

Mental health changing algorithms: a review on addiction and depression

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ABSTRACT

Over the last few decades, the use of social media has significantly increased. Additionally, this resulted in an increase of social media algorithms. The algorithms in social media are designed in a way that encourages users to stay on the platform. Algorithms bring a personalised experience to social media users. The more refined the user experience is, the more value the platform delivers to the user. This principle ensures that the user experience gets better, it also has its downside, for example the increase of addiction.

This paper focused on reviewing the influence of social media algorithms on mental health aspects such as social media addiction to depression, narrowed down to young adults in the Netherlands and three social media platforms that use a timeline-based approach.

The research results show no strong causal relation between the workings of algorithms on addiction and depression. Although most of the respondents acknowledged that the personal content generated by algorithms, made them spend more time on social media, only a few respondents felt like their happiness was influenced by it.

Keywords

Algorithms, Social Media, Depression, Addiction, Young Adults

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has been accompanied by a conspicuous increase of usage and time spent on social media platforms. Due to the pandemic, social media has evolved into a source of information through content created by users and algorithms.

A study by Rainie et al. (2022) has stated that social media platforms use algorithms to decide and structure what flow of content users see and to recommend content that a user might like. Thus, algorithms use data of the user in order to make a user's feed unique. This uniqueness is based on relevancy, which is determined by factors such as the behaviour of one's online social circle or "likes" (Digital Marketing Institute, 2022).

While social media may be beneficial, it also brings along negative consequences. For example, problematic internet use (PIU) and techno addiction are negative consequences of social media (Zheng & Lee, 2016). PIU occurs when the psychological, social, school, and/or work life of an individual is adversely affected due to the use of the internet (Beard & Wolf, 2001). Whilst techno addiction is a type of stress caused by an irrepensible need to always use technology excessively everywhere and for extended periods of time (Salanova, Llorens, & Cifre, 2013). Additionally, numerous studies in the pre-pandemic state have been conducted into social media usage among young adults. These studies observed a positive correlation between addiction and depression due to active social media usage (Haand & Shuwang, 2020).

According to WHO (2022) the pandemic had in particular an impact on the mental health of young adults. On average, young adults are spending three hours per day on social media (Kemp, 2022, p.12), which means that social media algorithms could be more unique and advanced than before the pandemic. It is, however, unclear to which extent this growth in social media algorithms translates into an increase in addiction and depression. Hence, there is a need to consider to what extent social media algorithms influence the relation

between social media addiction and depression among young adults. Initially, this paper discusses how algorithms work. Then, it looks at the influence of algorithms in social media on addiction in current literature. Followed by the influence of algorithms in social media on depression is discussed. And at last, the link is made between addiction and depression to discuss the possible influence of algorithms on this.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

In the same way that users shape the direction of the platform, likewise the platform shapes the user's behaviour and social standing (Dijck, 2013). The shaping of the platform is based on algorithms. Algorithms change on the basis of relevancy. In the setting of social media, the relevancy is determined by factors, such as the behaviour of one's online social circle or "likes". The purpose of an algorithm is to eliminate irrelevant content or content that is not of high quality for the user (Digital Marketing Institute, 2022). Due to the accessibility and ease of use of social media, reliance on digital media has been increasing over the past few years, leading to an increase in social media usage as well.

Existing literature states that the increase of usage in social media could have either a positive or negative influence on the mental health of a user, depending on active and passive usage (Valkenburg, Van Driel, & Beyens (2022). Additionally, a study by Sert & Başkale (2022) found a positive correlation between the increased time spent by students on social media during the pandemic and a rise in social media addiction among those students. The study concluded that the amount of daily time spent on social media before the pandemic and during the pandemic was found to be positively correlated (Sert & Başkale, 2022).

Currently, in the post-pandemic state, empirical research about social media addiction and depression is missing, especially on young adults. The age range 18 to 25, is generally defined as young adulthood (Simpson, 2018). Young adults are an essential group of users because the majority of the group grew up with digital communications technology (nngroup, 2016) and are using social media as part of everyday life (Kemp, 2022). As majority users, young adults are more likely to participate and finish (online) surveys than other age groups of society. Therefore, in this study key factors within mental health are *addiction* to social media and *depression* due to social media among young adults (aged 18 to 25).

A knowledge gap is found due to the unclearness the influence of social media algorithms have on the relationship of social media addiction to

depression among young adults. Whereas the influence was known, it would be possible for companies to adjust their health policies accordingly to depressed young (adult) workers. Another advantage for diminishing this knowledge gap could be that by gaining new insights, social media platforms redesign how the algorithms function in order to decrease depression or detect depression among users in general.

Research questions

The knowledge gap led to the following central research question:

“Do social media algorithms have an influence on the relationship between social media addiction and depression among young adults?”

To answer this central research question, the following sub questions were formulated:

Sub Questions

1. Do social media users realise the effects of algorithms on their feed?
2. What is the relationship between Social Media use and addiction?
3. What is the relationship between Social Media Use and depression?

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Addiction is an uncontrollable habit or use of a substance which could become harmful (NHS, 2021). In every form of addiction, the dopamine system is activated, giving a person a rewarding feeling. When the addiction becomes a habit, the dopamine receptors will decrease and mostly respond to a rewarding feeling given after certain habitual action was taken i.e., the addiction (Wise & Robble, 2020).

The study by the NHS focuses on the addiction to social media, which has several predictors. A study by the NHS in 2017 discovered that younger people in general are more likely to become addicted to social media. Other contributing factors are extraversion, neuroticism and attachment style. Extraversion solely is not an exact predictor; it may be a predictor to social media usage because of the craving for attention but does not necessarily lead to addiction. A neurotic person may be more likely to become addicted, however, attachment style mediated the neuroticism predictor. Furthermore, anxious and avoidant attachment styles were predictors as well, but when fear of missing out (FOMO) was included in this research' model, these attachment styles became irrelevant. FOMO predicts social media use and addiction regardless of personality traits and attachment style (Blackwell et al., 2017).

Human behaviour

As stated above, FOMO is a major contributing factor to social media addiction. Research has shown that envy partially mediates FOMO, meaning that an addicted person may have less negative side effects, like FOMO, when being less envious or vice versa (Yin et al., 2021). Furthermore, research into demographic factors, narcissism and self-esteem showed significant influence on addiction; lower education, being female, young, having narcissistic traits and a negative self-concept all contributed to a higher change of social media addiction (Andreassen et al., 2017).

Social media algorithms

Algorithms are essentially tools that can assist us in problem solving and are often erroneously linked to computers. However, algorithms date back to ancient Babylon. An algorithm is like a series of actions taken in a certain order and those steps can just as well be completed on paper (Louridas, 2020).

Depression

To measure depression multiple instruments are commonly used, like the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale (CES-D) or EQ-5D (APA, 2019). For this study, the focus will be on daily functioning and general interest in hobbies or activities (Pozuelo & Stein, 2021).

Conceptual model

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

The relationships between the variables are shown above in figure 1. The following hypotheses will be tested in this research. The goal of this study is to investigate whether H3 is true.

H1: Social media addiction has a negative influence on developing depression.

H2: Social media algorithms have a negative influence on the relationship of addiction and depression.

H3: Human behaviour has an effect on the relationship between Social Media addiction and depression.

METHODOLOGY

An explanatory research method is chosen to test theories of association (Scribbr, 2022). Primary data is collected by using a digital questionnaire, which will be sent to young adults from 18 to 25 years old, living in the Netherlands. The main focus is to collect individual experiences from users of social media, therefore the unit of analysis of this research is young adults. Secondary data will be provided using existing academic and other scientific literature regarding topics such as mental health, algorithms and social media.

The following topics are included in the questionnaire; human characteristics and their behaviour (like FOMO (Przybylski, 2013)), addiction, depression, algorithms and the perceived impact of the algorithm on the user's state of being. A Likert-scale (interval) will be used, to be able to perform cross comparisons between the variables and to establish a consistent framework for the entire survey. Closed-ended questions and quantitative questions are listed, to be able to make unanimous statements.

To conclude if a respondent is addicted or depressed, off-the-shelf measures are used. The advantages for using those are the proven validity and reliability (Bruner et al., 2015), which will be used for the variables addiction and depression. Young (1999) describes eight domains that can be considered as criteria for an addict, with fulfilment in five of these areas being considered addicted. However, nine addiction questions were developed in the survey, two of which were in the same area 'environmental problems (family, school, work, friends)'. Only respondents who answered "yes" to both of these two questions were included in labelling as addicted in the results section.

To measure depression, Well-Being was used. When a respondent has a raw score below 13 or if the patient has answered 0 to 1 to any of the five items, there is a big chance that person is struggling with depression (WHO, 1998).

According to Centraal Bureau Statistiek, 1,558,000 young adults are present in the Netherlands (CBS, 2022). Using an interval of 95% (with related z-

value of 1.96), the calculated sample size would be
 $384 \rightarrow \frac{1,558,000 * 1.96^2 * 50 * 50}{1.96^2 * 50 * 50 + 1,557,999 * 5^2}$.

Working of social media algorithms

Social media has had a big impact on society. It has helped connect people globally and provides easy access to different types of information (Burhan & Moradzadeh, 2020). Algorithms in social media make recommendations and selections of posts for users to look at. The algorithm also links people with others. With the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in social media the experience becomes more personal (Leonardi & Vaast, 2017).

These technologies allow aggregation, abstraction, and categorization into consumer profiles. The categories derived from user's online actions are projected back onto them, enframing them in an "algorithmic identity". This identity formation works through mathematical algorithms to infer categories of identity on users (Bhandari & Bimo, 2022).

Overuse of the platforms and the application of algorithms may be detrimental to the physical and mental well-being. This can dramatically affect individuals' wellbeing, either positively or negatively (Burhan & Moradzadeh, 2020). Digital services often lead to time-consuming activities and habits. Digital service consumption compared to other services often comes with very low entry barriers. Simply downloading a new app, trying out a streaming service, or registering on a social media platform takes seconds and requires little resource investment (Fritze, Eisingerich & Benkenstein, 2019). Another disadvantage of social media is that it can cause addiction. This is perpetuated through feedback loop mechanisms acting through the dopamine reward system (Burhan & Moradzadeh, 2020).

Social media platforms use powerful AI that are fed by the vast flows of digital content that may be used to analyse user behaviour, mental state, and physical context. New forms of AI-generated content and AI-driven virtual agents present new forms of risks in social media use, the harm of which will be difficult to predict (Lewis & Moorkens, 2020).

According to Lewis & Moorkens (2020) risks of algorithmic selection are identified as:

- Manipulation of individuals or groups
- Diminishing variety that creates biased views and distortion of reality
- Constraints on communication and freedom of expression
- Threats to privacy and data protection rights
- Social discrimination
- Violation of intellectual property rights

- Impact on the human brain and cognitive capacity
- Algorithmic power over human behaviour and development

Relationship between social media use and addiction

Social media use could lead to addiction, whereby users, regardless of their context, manifest symptoms of behavioural addiction (Hawi & Sawaha, 2017). Social media addiction is the compulsive use of social media sites or applications that demonstrates itself in behavioural addiction symptoms. Those symptoms are tolerance, conflict, withdrawal, rebounds, and mood modification (Griffiths, 2005).

A person is considered to be addicted to internet use when weekly hours spent online are 21.2 hours or higher (Yang & Tung, 2007).

When this amount is reached while using social media, and a minimum of five questions are answered as "yes", a person could be considered as a social media addict.

- "1. Do you feel preoccupied with the Internet (frequently thinking about previous on-line activity or anticipating your next on-line session)?
2. Do you feel the need to spend increasing amounts of time online to maintain the same level of satisfaction from your Internet use?
3. Have you repeatedly tried unsuccessfully to control, cut back, or completely stop your Internet use?
4. Do you feel restless, moody, depressed, or irritable when attempting to control your Internet use?
5. Do you frequently stay on-line longer than originally intended?
6. Have you jeopardised or risked the loss of a significant relationship, job, educational, or career opportunity because of the Internet?
7. Have you lied to family members, a therapist, or others to conceal the extent of your Internet use?
8. Do you use the Internet to escape from problems or relieve a dysphoric mood (such as feelings of helplessness, guilt, anxiety, depression)?"

Relationship between social media use and depression

Social media use and depression are significantly intertwined, meaning that young adults who use social media more are also more often depressed. A study by Lin et al., (2016) however did not distinguish if depressed people use social media more or if social media directly causes depression, but a strong correlation was proved. A similar conclusion was drawn in a different study where passive social media use was researched in context to depression, also concluding that it was unclear if

social media use caused depression or vice versa (Aalbers et al., 2019). As stated earlier in the research and as can be seen in the model (figure 1), other variables are present for social media to cause depression.

Vulnerability of young adults to depression

According to CBS the mental health of young adults (18 to 25 years old) declined when compared to 2016 (CBS, 2021). However, this does not necessarily mean that young adults are more likely to get depressed. A study on subjective age and depression found that people who feel younger than their actual age, are less likely to be depressed (Debrecezen & Bailey, 2021). Regarding objective age, studies found that during Covid-19 young adults were more likely to develop depressive symptoms (Wang et al., 2020). A similar result was found in a Canadian study that showed that anxiety, stress and depressive symptoms were higher among young adults, but also with ages 60 and above (Nwachukwu et al., 2020). These studies, however, were conducted during the Covid pandemic and may not be applicable in a 'normal' situation. Without any more evidence, it cannot be concluded that young adults are more likely to be depressed.

Depression in young adults

According to CBS nine percent of young adults had a heightened risk of being depressed in 2020 (CBS, 2021).

RESULTS

For the results a survey was conducted, consisting of a total of 65 respondents in the target age group. 55.4% of the respondents were female, 43.1% were male and 1.5% chose other. The mean age of the respondents is 21.1. The minimum age set for the survey was at 18 and the maximum at 25.

46.2% of the respondents mentioned the word algorithms. 30.8% of the respondents think their feed is built by data from likes, clicks, activities etc. 4.6% filled in cookies. 3.1% of the respondents think their feed is built by companies. 1.5% of the respondents think their feed is built by the popularity of the content. 13.9% did not answer the question.

Respondents were all asked the question: "why do you use social media?"

Table 1. Why do you use social media?

To find funny or entertaining content	89.2%
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To stay in touch with what friends are doing	75.4%
To stay up to date with news and current events	69.2%
To fill up spare time	61.5%
To share photos or videos with others	38.5%
General networking with other people	27.7%
Because friends are already on them	18.5%
To research new products to buy	12.30%
To meet new people	9.2%
To share my opinion	6.2%

RQ1: Do social media users realise the effects of algorithms on their feed?

To answer this research question, the survey questioned subjects about their knowledge of algorithms and how the subjects think about the way they operate in social media (Full survey in appendix 1). Most respondents (about 75%) agreed or strongly agreed to using social media more because of the personal content (see table 2). Besides that, 43% of the respondents realised that algorithms have an influence on their feed without the word being mentioned before in the survey. Furthermore, statements about the effect of personalised content on the subject's wellbeing was questioned in Q16_2 and Q16_3. As seen in the table, almost half of the respondents agreed that the personalised content made them feel addicted. When asked what positive effects on happiness the personalised content had, most of the respondents felt that it didn't have any influence on their happiness.

Table 2. Wellbeing due to personalised content

	Q15_1:	Q15_2:	Q16_1:	Q16_2:	Q16_3:
Strongly agree	37%	23%	2%	2%	0%

Agree	54%	51%	15%	48%	23%
Neither agree nor disagree	8%	17%	55%	18%	52%
Disagree	0%	6%	25%	26%	22%
Strongly disagree	2%	3%	3%	6%	3%

RQ2: What is the relationship between Social Media use and addiction?

65 of the 73 respondents used at least one type of the targeted social media platforms; Instagram, Facebook and TikTok. 93.8% of those respondents used Instagram, 49.2% used Facebook and 46.2% used TikTok.

Regarding addiction, 90.8% of those respondents stated that they frequently stayed online longer than originally intended. 92.3% stated that they never lied to family members, a therapist, or others to conceal the extent of their social media use.

10 of the 65 people answered five or more times 'yes' to the eight addiction questions in the survey. And 4 of those 10 people used social media more than 21.2 hours per week, so could be considered addicted.

RQ3: What is the relationship between Social Media Use and depression?

To get insights about the well-being of the respondents, four statements were stated. The respondents had to respond to these statements by indicating to what extent they agreed upon each statement. In view of the internal validity, the respondents were not told that these statements were indicators of depression.

The remarkable outcomes have been listed below:

49% of the respondents often felt cheerful and in good spirits, while none responded not at all.

The majority (46%) stated that they sometimes felt calm and relaxed.

What stood out with the third statement "*I woke up feeling fresh and rested*" was that also with this statement the majority (49.2%) felt that they sometimes woke up feeling fresh and rested, while 7.7% stated not at all. The last statement had an outcome of 45% of the respondents agreeing that they often feel that their daily life has been filled with things that they are interested in.

DISCUSSION

This work adds to the body of information in the existing literature and serves as a foundation for future research. There are a few limitations to this study. Social media platforms keep their algorithms private. For this reason, the exact working of the algorithms could not be found. There weren't many scholarly papers available to support informal sources of the working of social media algorithms. The survey was shared via the network of the researchers. It was shared via group chats and Instagram. 65 respondents answered the survey, thus the predetermined sample size of 384 respondents was not achieved. This was due to a lack of time. Therefore, this research is not generalisable for the target audience in this study. There were no respondents who were depressed according to the results of the survey. For this reason, the RQ cannot be answered.

It is not certain that the results of the survey are reliable. The respondents might be ashamed of how much they use social media and lie to themselves by filling in a lower number of hours than they use social media in reality. It could also be hard to answer questions about depression honestly.

CONCLUSION

The research results show no strong causal relation between the workings of algorithms on addiction and depression. Although most of the respondents acknowledged that the personal content, generated by algorithms, made them spend more time on social media, only a few respondents felt like their happiness was influenced by it. The majority of respondents, however, did reply to be feeling addicted due to the personalised content shown on their social media feed.

There were no respondents with a strong indication of depression. As a result, the hypotheses are rejected, noting that the required sample size was not achieved. Follow-up research is needed to understand the influence of external factors, such as the season of the year the questionnaire was performed, level of education of the respondents and side activities that the respondents undertook.

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APPENDIX 1 - SURVEY**General Questions****Q1 What is your gender?**

- Women
- Men
- Other _____

Q2 What is your age?

Not Applicable

10 25 40 55 70

Age	
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Q3 Are you living in the Netherlands?

- Yes
- No

Q4 Which of these social media platforms do you use?

Facebook

Instagram

TikTok

None

Q5 Could you give a reason why you do not use these types of social media?

Social media use

Q6 On average, how many hours do you spend weekly on social media?

Q7 In line with the time you spend on social media, can you indicate how often you do the following activities?

	Not at all	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
Post content	<input type="radio"/>				
Like content	<input type="radio"/>				
Share content with others	<input type="radio"/>				
Watch the content	<input type="radio"/>				

Q8 What social media platform do you spend the most time on?

Order the following from most (1) to least (3) used. If you only use one type of social media, make that number 1, and ignore the others.

_____ Facebook

_____ Instagram

_____ TikTok

Q9 Why do you use social media?

- To stay in touch with what friends are doing
- To stay up-to-date with news and current events
- To fill up spare time
- To find funny or entertaining content
- Because friends are already on them
- To share photos or videos with others
- To share my opinion
- To research new products to buy
- To meet new people
- General networking with other people

Q10 How do you think the content on your feed gets generated?

End of Block: Social media use

Start of Block: Social Media Addiction

Q11 Please read the following statements and answer yes or no based on your feelings.

	Yes	No
1. Do you feel preoccupied with social media (frequently thinking about previous social media activity or anticipating your next social media session)?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Do you feel the need to spend increasing amounts of time online to maintain the same level of satisfaction from your social media use?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Have you repeatedly tried unsuccessfully to control, cut back, or completely stop your social media use?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q12 Please read the following statements and answer yes or no based on your feelings.

	Yes	No
4. Do you frequently stay online on social media longer than originally intended?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Have you jeopardised or risked the loss of a significant relationship, job, educational, or career opportunity because of social media?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Do you feel restless, moody, depressed, or irritable when attempting to control your social media use?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q13 Please read the following statements and answer yes or no based on your feelings.

	Yes	No
7. Have you lied to family members, a therapist, or others to conceal the extent of your social media use?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. Do you use social media to escape from problems or relieve a dysphoric mood (such as feelings of helplessness, guilt, anxiety, depression)?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

9. Ignored your partner, family members, or friends because of social media?

Depression

Q14 Please fill in how you have felt for the past two weeks.

	Not at all	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
I have felt cheerful and in good spirits	<input type="radio"/>				
I felt calm and relaxed	<input type="radio"/>				
I woke up feeling fresh and rested	<input type="radio"/>				
My daily life has been filled with things that interest me.	<input type="radio"/>				

Algorithms & Feelings**Q15 Rate your level of agreement with each statement**

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1. I would spend less time on social media if the content did not match my interests.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. The personal content makes me use social media more.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q16 Rate your level of influence with each statement

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
3. Social media has a positive influence on my happiness.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. The personalised content is making me feel addicted.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

5. The personalised content is influencing my happiness positively.

